

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THEORETICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR USING THE CONCEPT OF "SYSTEM" IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS

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Abstract

The article focuses on scientific interpretations of the concept of the pedagogical process in scientific sources, and also comments on the shortcomings. Based on the findings of the research process, it is more expedient to reveal the essence of the concepts "system", "structure", "holistic", "subsystem" - the perception of the pedagogical process as an integral system.

The paper provides a scientific substantiation of the theoretical and technological foundations for using the concept of "system" in the management of the pedagogical process in accordance with the generalizations formed on the basis of the development of materials obtained in the course of the study.

Keywords: pedagogical process, system, structure, part, subsystem, holistic, education, education, principle.

Relevance of the research topic

Based on the study of scientific sources, it is concluded that there are a number of errors and discrepancies in the interpretation of the concept of the pedagogical process. Among the reasons for these shortcomings is the fact that the "pedagogical process" is not considered as a system. The approach to this concept not as a system leads to theoretical and technological "gaps" in the problem of its management and, as a result, makes inevitable difficulties in the work of practicing teachers in this area. Therefore, we argue that the definition of the theoretical and technological basis for the use of the concept of "system" in the management of the pedagogical process is an urgent pedagogical problem.

Interpretation of the research material

In many well-known scientific sources, the concept of "pedagogical process" is presented as "the interaction of teachers and students to achieve the goal" and it is emphasized that the social experience acquired in the pedagogical process becomes a personality quality. We agree with this opinion.

By the way, it should be noted that in some pedagogical sources, instead of this concept, the word "educational process" is used. Studies show that this concept is narrow, incomplete, does not reflect the complexity of the process, especially its completeness and universality. In our opinion, "ensuring the unity of teaching, education, upbringing and development on the basis of completeness and universality" is the essence of the pedagogical process. In the latest pedagogical literature, this concept is presented as a "holistic pedagogical process". This is natural, because training, education, upbringing and development are not separate processes. They are integral parts of a single pedagogical process that serves the same purpose. We want to emphasize that the unity of education, upbringing, education and development, that is, the unity of the pedagogical process, does not negate the specifics of these concepts, the characteristics of each. On the contrary, it

is important to have a deep understanding of the essence and main functions of training, education, upbringing and development separately. Not because we want to separate and oppose them, but because we want to penetrate deep into the essence of these processes, to understand their true dialectical connections and interactions; without their detailed understanding it is impossible to organize training, training, education or development as efficiently as possible, to turn it into a controlled cognitive or technological process.

Based on the materials obtained in the course of the study, we conclude that it is expedient to interpret the essence of the concept of the pedagogical process with a "system-structural" approach that is effective from the point of view of managing this process. First, we briefly comment on this approach ("system-structural" approach) on the basis of scientific sources.

The system is a set of interconnections of its constituent elements and, in its logical volume, belongs to such a general concept that it can be attributed to any object, event or process..[8; 88]. "Complete" and "system" are often explained by species-sex logical relationships, sometimes used as synonyms, and sometimes considered the pinnacle of an entirely new system. A system is a whole that includes both elements and relationships between elements.

To define a system, at least two points are necessary: a) mentally isolate a part from the whole; b) look at the system as an organic connection, the totality of its elements and their integration.

Each system has its own structure and function, which this structure carries. The system can be considered as a whole, consisting of the totality of its structure and function. [11; 145]. In principle, any system enters another system as an element and subsystem with a higher, more complex integrity. [4; 107]. Each system acts as a lower structural level than itself, as a more perfect system than the existing system.

What we have said can be taken as the methodological basis of the pedagogical process itself and its directions.

Despite the foregoing, we can say that the pedagogical process is a holistic and complex system. It also consists of a number of subsystems: the training process; educational process; formation process; development process; the process of cooperation between teachers and students; the system of conditions in which the pedagogical process takes place; a system of forms and methods for the implementation of the pedagogical process, etc. [9; 94].

The completeness of the pedagogical process is ensured in various ways: by the integrity of the individual; with the unity of purpose and content in training, upbringing and education; presence of driving forces and patterns.

In real life, a person's personality is not formed in parts, his mental qualities do not develop separately from his moral qualities. The moral qualities that characterize the personality interact with each other, one contributes to the formation of the other. [3; 30-31].

A variety of socially useful activities in the pedagogical process is the most important condition for the comprehensive development of the child's personality. Therefore, activities are connected in the pedagogical process. The completeness of the pedagogical process is explained not only by the unity of ideas, morality, aesthetics, labor, physical and mental education, but also by the inner harmony of each of them. [4; 199].

Summarizing our opinion, we consider it expedient to succinctly classify the factors that determine the completeness of the pedagogical process into two groups: 1) having the same purpose and content in training, education, upbringing, containing driving forces and patterns; 2) commonality of principles, methods, forms of organization of training, education, upbringing. This commonality allows these processes to correspond in purpose and content to the completeness of the pedagogical process. [9; 98].

The processes within the pedagogical process serve one purpose. The complex dialectic of relations within the pedagogical process is manifested in the processes themselves. This dialectic is manifested in the unity and independence of the processes, in the unity of the systems included in it, in their direct or indirect subordination to each other, in the preservation of their generality and specificity.

Understanding the pedagogical process as an integral system directs the movement of morality in terms of defining and arguing the theoretical foundations of its management. The theoretical foundations identified by us in the development of research materials are: 1) the need for subsystems to correspond to the emergent nature of the pedagogical process, 2) the basis for the expectation of the dialectics of the components that make up the system (goal, content, activity, result components) in determining the logic of management and implementation of the process; 3) subsystems depending on the nature of the whole have different characteristics, for example, embedded systems; 4) dependence on the main features of both in regulating relations between subsystems, 5) the position of each subsystem in

the system in accordance with the basic requirements-principles arising from general pedagogical dependencies.

On the basis of the theoretical foundations of the management of the pedagogical process, its technology is implemented. [4; 201-202]

From the research process (especially from the study of scientific sources and our many years of experience), we conclude that the completeness of the pedagogical process is also expressed in the principles of training and education. There are principles that apply to both teaching and education. [3; 34].

It should be noted that for the implementation of control from a technological point of view, it is especially important to know the full pattern of principles. Otherwise, using the completeness of the concept of "system", one could make mistakes in the purposeful formation of the technology for managing the pedagogical process. Therefore, it is necessary to get to the bottom of each principle. To clarify our point of view, let's look at some of the principles.

The principle of activity, consciousness and independence by its very nature is associated with the condition of choosing means in accordance with the content. Consciousness is the ability to understand internal connections, especially causal relationships, to deduce the essence, to consider the purpose of the activity and ways to achieve it. "Why is that?", "What if it were different?", "How else could it be?" Thinking about such questions is connected with consciousness. Activity and awareness are so intertwined that it is very difficult to erect a barrier between them. Self-reliance is measured by the nature of the relationship between teacher and student. [1; 222-223].

The teacher-practitioner should know that the conditions for the active and conscious acquisition of knowledge by students are as follows: if the student is able to prove what he says, if he is able to present original evidence, then knowledge is obtained consciously and actively; if the student is able to apply knowledge in the same way as in standard conditions, as well as in modified conditions, then he has mastered them in a state of consciousness and active activity; if the student is able to present the material in his own words, in a modified form, then he has mastered it consciously and actively; if a student is able to independently use the acquired knowledge to obtain new knowledge, then he has mastered them in a state of awareness and active activity, etc. [10].

It is known that the team acts in full accordance with the general goal of the pedagogical process, holds events and performs socially useful work. The teacher, as an experienced and knowledgeable person, must give the right direction in the organization and conduct of all this work.

The principle of consistency and consistency is essentially connected with the principle of an integrated approach. Systematization in the pedagogical process means, first of all, the expectation of the system, its consideration. For example, the teacher should systematically take into account the internal connection of scientific concepts in the learning process, the connection between its branches and components in education. [4;

215]. Systematics expresses the logic of the subject itself. Each subject has a system of interrelated and derived concepts. [7; 102].

Supplementing data in knowledge lessons, formed educational qualities by extracurricular activities, developing a unified system of pedagogical influence, creating a connection between the work of educators, observing the internal logic of the subject - all this is included in the concept of "systematic". The concept of "sequence" is different from systematic. The main condition here is that the relationships closely follow each other.

The principle of integration of training and education, which is an important tool in the development of technologies for managing the pedagogical process, also follows from an integrated approach. The principle of an integrated approach to education requires the coordination of the activities of institutions and persons involved in education, as well as the work carried out in various areas of education, and now the same requirement applies to schooling. All subjects should be taught in an interactive form, and all forms of education should be organized: individual work with students, counseling, subject circles, excursions, homework, etc. should be combined into one stream.

If the function of education is to help students understand life, then the function of education is to shape their attitude towards life. Knowledge is the basis of relationships, and attitude, in turn, is an important factor in obtaining new knowledge. There is no relation isolated from knowledge, no knowledge isolated from relation. First of all, this objective connection of relationship with knowledge requires the teacher to always take these two concepts into an internal connection. On the other hand, both education and upbringing serve the same purpose. The unity of purpose leads to the fact that these two concepts complement each other and are a condition for each other. There are even issues that at first glance are difficult to distinguish whether they relate to training or education (for example, the development of aesthetic and physical strength).

Ensuring the unity of exactingness with respect for the individual is an immutable rule of educational work. Only exactingness to the student, forgetting about the need to respect his personality, leads to failures in educational work. This fact is even more pronounced in teaching. A teacher who cares about the student during the lesson, kind, able to make concessions, always succeeds if he does not forget about his seriousness and exactingness. This confirms that the unity of respect and exactingness is a general principle of the pedagogical process, and not a particular principle of any of its branches. At the same time, this idea can be applied to the principle of addressing a person through identifying his positive aspects. In pedagogy, it is known that a teacher who reveals the positive side of a person and turns to this side can have a strong impact on his psychology and eliminate shortcomings. An educator who does not see good in a person, but only emphasizes his shortcomings, lays the foundation for failure in educational work. At the same time, just as a teacher who does not take into account the age and individual characteristics of his students may not succeed

in teaching, a teacher who ignores this principle also faces difficulties. It would be more correct to speak about the general nature of the principle of accessibility inherent in the pedagogical process.

The completeness of the pedagogical process is realized due to the commonality of the components. The main goal of education, which is part of a full-fledged pedagogical process, is not only to ensure the assimilation of knowledge by students, but also to motivate students to purposeful socially useful activities, to develop their ability to consciously and persistently overcome difficulties and obstacles, to create conditions for the full development of the personality of students. Education, like training, has three functions - purely educational, teaching and developing. [4; 203].

In the learning process, the formation of scientific concepts, ideas, laws and theories, skills and abilities takes place, and in the process of educating morality, ideas, aesthetics, etc., the formation of qualities, rules, socially significant attitudes, behavior patterns prevails. As training and education determine the mental development of children, so development contributes to the success of training and education. The specificity of the processes involved in a full-fledged pedagogical process is manifested in the definition of its main functions. The main function of the learning process is to teach, the main function of the educational process is to receive education, the main function of the educational process is to teach, and the main function of the development process is to develop. Each of these processes performs other functions in the entire pedagogical process.

The interaction of the dialectic of relations is manifested in the purpose, tasks, content, forms and methods of processes carried out in connection with each other.

The formation of scientific concepts, laws and theories, skills and habits prevails in the learning process. They have a great influence on education and personal development. In the process of extracurricular and extracurricular activities, the formation of moral qualities, beliefs, norms, rules, ideals, their evaluative orientation prevails. At the same time, imagination, knowledge and skills are formed. Thus, the main goal in both processes is to serve the formation of personality. However, each of these processes helps to achieve the goal by its own means.

The specificity of the processes is reflected in the forms and methods chosen to achieve the goal. If more forms of classroom work are used in teaching, then other various characteristic forms of work predominate in extracurricular and out-of-school education. The methods of achieving the goal are the same, but the methods of control and self-control are different. The commonality of educational methods is one of the important factors that ensure the integrity of the pedagogical process. Methods such as lectures, interviews, etc., which serve to understand the new educational material, are consistent with the methods of persuasion used in education. Compliance is manifested not only in the names of these methods, but also in their purposes and methods of application. In educational work, such methods of persuasion as interviews, lectures, debates,

etc. are used. In the first case, i.e. in teaching, students are mainly focused on specific knowledge, and in the second etc. qualities. In the first case, the student directly feels the result; in the second case, he may not feel the educational effect directly. This idea can be visualized in a problem situation. The task of the teacher is to direct students to solve the problem, encourage students to think independently and turn the solution of the problem into their goal. A student who finds a solution in a lesson even rejoices and can cope with other situations of the same nature. [4; 204], [12; 125-128]

The unity of training and education is manifested in practical methods. Practical methods, especially various forms and types of independent work, are used both in teaching and in education. In the organization of independent work of students, both in teaching and in upbringing, sometimes there is a great need for the usual voluntary effort, the desire to be goal-oriented, and not for the skills necessary for the successful implementation of practical work.

Although training and education have their own characteristics and responsibilities, they serve to form the unity of the student's personality. In the formation of mental processes, it is not enough to separate the functions of education and upbringing; another psychological development is just as important for the success of education as the development of logical thinking. [2; 105].

The spiritual forces, including the will, of a student accustomed to thinking and imagining both in concepts and images, are constantly mobilized. He easily advances in the pedagogical process and therefore feels happy. The joy of learning and education is what drives his future success. It's the same with memory. [3; 37]

The commonality of the forms of organization of training and education allows them to be combined in terms of content and purpose, in terms of the completion of the pedagogical process.

The relationship of training, education, training and development, creating a basis for each other, enhances the completeness of the pedagogical process, determines the effectiveness of each goal.

Scientific novelty of research work

The "system-structural" perspective of the pedagogical process is explained and the theoretical and technological foundations for using the concept of "system" in the management of the pedagogical process are determined.

Practical significance of the research work

The definition of the theoretical and technological basis for the use of an integral feature of the concept of "system" in the management of the pedagogical process will have a positive impact on the formation of an environment that includes the elimination of shortcomings in management. this process.

The result

The "system-structural" approach to the pedagogical process raises the scientific level of its disclosure, argues for the definition of the theoretical and technological basis for its management.

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